

INSTITUTE FOR
EUROPEAN
STUDIES

Working | paper

The EL-CSID project is coordinated by the Institute for European Studies (IES)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693799.

Case study report

The Perception of the EU Cultural and Science Diplomacy in Turkey

Naciye Selin Senocak
Centre d'Études Diplomatiques et Stratégiques Türkiye (CEDS Türkiye)

Issue 2018/14 • April 2018

Table of contents

1. Introduction

- 1.1. Objectives of the study
- 1.2. Methodology
- 1.3. Team

2. Cultural Diplomacy

- 2.1. Definition and impact of Culture
- 2.2. Cultural Exchange
- 2.3. Actions to further cross-cultural understanding
- 2.4. Sense of Belonging
- 2.5. Perceptions of European Values

3. Science Diplomacy

- 3.1. Perception of EU Scientific Diplomacy
- 3.2. Benefits of Science Cooperation
- 3.3. Gender Issue

4. Empirical results from the qualitative interviews

- 4.1. Perception of and involvement in EU projects
- 4.2. The influence of EU projects
- 4.3. Obstacles and problems that participants experienced in EU projects

5. Conclusion

1. Introduction

The study is undertaken in the framework of the European Leadership in Cultural, Science and Innovation Diplomacy (EL-CSID) project. This project has the ambition to codify and articulate the relevance of cultural, science and innovation diplomacy for EU external relations as part of a systematic and strategic approach. It aims to identify how the Union and its member states might collectively and individually develop a good institutional and strategic policy environment for extra-regional culture and science diplomacy.

The overarching objectives of this project are threefold:

1. To detail and analyse the manner in which the EU operates in the domains of cultural and science diplomacy in the current era; comparing its bilateral and multilateral cultural and science ties with other states, regions, and public and private international organisations.
2. To examine the degree to which cultural, science and innovation diplomacy can enhance the interests of the EU in the contemporary world order and specifically, to identify:
 - a) How cultural and science diplomacy can contribute to Europe's standing as an international actor;
 - b) Opportunities offered by enhanced coordination and collaboration amongst the EU, its members and their extra-European partners;
 - c) Constraints, both existing and evolving, posed by economic and socio-political factors affecting the operating environments of both science and cultural diplomacy.
3. To identify a series of mechanisms/platforms to raise awareness among relevant stakeholders of the importance of science and culture as vehicles for enhancing the EU's external relations. The research generates both scholarly work and policy-oriented output, which is disseminated through an extensive and targeted dissemination programme.

Together, these objectives should not only contribute to a strengthening of EU policy towards the use of science, culture and innovation in its wider diplomacy, but also to a deepening of scholarly understanding of diplomacy as an abiding, if changing, institution. To these ends, EL-CSID marshals an empirical and analytical narrative to offer practical support to the further development and enhancement of the EU's science, cultural and innovation diplomacy. It studies the current and future role of science, innovation and cultural diplomacy as a feature of its foreign relations through a program of historical stocktaking and multidisciplinary and cross-national comparative research.

As such, the current survey forms an important insight into the ways in which neighbourhood countries think and behave in this area, as well as providing benchmarks against which future evolutions can be tracked.

1.1 Objectives of the study

Work Package 4, Task 3 is entitled 'the view of the EU cultural and science diplomacy from the outside'. It is an impact study that wants to show how the EU's cultural and science diplomacy is perceived in the MENA countries (Tunisia and Egypt) and Turkey. The primary question was: what do the EU's partners think of its approach to science, innovation and its enhancement of external cultural relations? The main objective was thus to measure the degree to which populations notice and appreciate European cultural and science diplomacy actions.

Through interviews (qualitative study) and survey (quantitative study), WP4 Task 3 is a measurement of the reception of the EU's messages in the considered countries. This study aims at understanding better the partners' image of the EU.

This report examines the following themes in turn:

- How Turkish population conceives of the idea of culture and its importance to them.
- Issues of cultural exchange, specifically its value to society, the extent to which cross-cultural contact already occurs, the willingness of Turkish populations to meet people from European countries, ways in which cross-cultural understanding can be enhanced and actors best placed to implement these measures.
- Interest in culture both in Turkey and Europe, the perception on whether there is indeed a European culture, its characteristics and the effects upon it of globalisation.
- Opinion on key values to be preserved and reinforced in Turkish society as well as whether these are seen as similar with the European values.
- Perceptions of European cultural and science diplomacy in Turkey. The degree to which populations notice European cultural and science diplomacy actions; The role of women in new scientific partnerships, especially between MENA and the EU.
- Differences and commonalities between European cultural diplomacy and science diplomacy when contrasted with understandings of them in Turkey.

1.2 Methodology

The case study is based on both a qualitative study (interviews) and a quantitative study (survey).

For the **survey**, 300 samples have been collected and analysed. **Interviews** have been conducted in Turkey with 15 people engaged in European programmes, people having benefited from those programmes, or people well aware of the existence of them. Although these interviews cannot systematically measure the impact of science and cultural diplomacy, they can capture a very important aspect, namely bottom-up insights about the role of the cooperation and its effectiveness. Focusing on the perceptions and views of those who have a first-hand experience with EU projects can deliver valuable information about how they assess the impact of the collaboration on the institutions involved and on broader society.

1.3 Team

At CEDS Turkiye: Naciye Selin Senocak (Director), Zuhul Zeren (Research Fellow), Aysun Yörü (trainee)

For the **survey** (quantitative study), 300 samples have been collected and analysed. The survey was carried out by EL-CSID WP4 Team, conducted in Turkey, Sakarya Province, which is one of the most cosmopolite province (population: 932,706 formed by 22 ethnic groups).

We collected quantitative data from 300 participants representing different social classes. As much as possible, we tried to approach participants from different types of public institutions, which perform different roles.

The samples come from a population composed mostly of representatives of the public sectors and academic world: students, policy experts, project coordinators, working scientists, and bureaucrats as well as administrative staff members. The study has been led within the premises of different public institutions:

- Sakarya Governorship
- Sakarya University

- Regional Directorate of Education
- Regional Directorate of Agriculture
- Regional Directorate of Science and Technology
- Regional Directorate of Population and Immigration

The analysis of the results of the survey shows:

2. Cultural Diplomacy

In this short opening chapter, we examine two issues that are important in understanding the area of cultural values. Firstly, we analyse the nature of ‘culture’ itself, as expressed by the Turkish population polled in the survey when they were asked what concepts they associate with the word. Secondly, we look at culture as it relates to the individual through answers to a question posed on the importance it has to respondents personally.

2.1 Definition and Impact of Culture

Respondents were asked to carry out a word-association exercise, being asked what comes to mind spontaneously when thinking about culture¹. The answers given here subsequently grouped into pre-defined categories along with other similar answers.

In an exercise such as this, it is very much the case that within a given category, the open-ended answers given by respondents still encompass a wide range of notions. As just one example, the category of ‘traditions/languages/customs and social/cultural communities’ encompasses both generalised references to the existence of multiple cultural communities existing in one country and narrower references to cultural customs specific to one community.

The above chart shows that in Turkey, ‘culture’ is very much associated with the ‘*traditions, languages, customs and social or cultural communities*’, as mentioned by 65% of the respondents.

¹ QA13: What comes to your mind when you think about the word ‘culture’?

We also see that the idea of culture defining 'life style and manners' figures prominently. Just under 48% mention placing this category in second place. Slightly below this level, a fairly large proportion gives answers that are related more to values and beliefs (including philosophy and religion) 42% express ideas linked to 'civilisation' and 'history', with 33%.

Whilst it is evident that culture is very much thought of in terms of the traditions, customs, values and beliefs, it is still the case that notions of knowledge and science (30%) are nonetheless tied up with the idea of culture to some extent. More generalised ideas figure towards the end of the list, such as Museums, which are expressed by 3% and Leisure, sport, travel, fun by 4%.

Finally, but no less importantly, it is encouraging to note that negative reactions to the idea of culture, in the form of its dismissal as elitist or dull are extremely rare (2%). Furthermore, only 1% indicated that they are disinterested in culture, or that 'it is not for me'.

Three social and demographic factors are linked to the cultural concepts respondents hold. The age is an important factor – as age increases, the more likely a respondent is to think of culture in terms of the **traditions, languages, customs and social or cultural communities**. For example, such ideas are expressed by 12% of those aged 15-24 and 57% of those aged 40-54. This relationship only holds true up to a point, as between the latter group and the 55+ age bracket, the percentage mentioning the traditions drops by 28 percentage points, to 29%.

2.2 Cultural Exchange

In this section, we examine the issue of cultural exchange. That globalisation has brought about increased contact between cultures is not in doubt. First of all, the discussion focuses on opinion on the role and value of cultural exchange. After this, we examine issues related to personal cultural exchange: The type and extent of contact people have with those in other countries, their interest in meeting people from other European countries and their willingness to learn new languages. Finally, we examine how cultural exchange can be further encouraged – both in terms of actions that would bring this about and actors who are well-placed to do this.

Here, we examine the extent of the European values influences over Turkish population². The large majority of respondents agree that European values have influenced the Turkish culture in different extent (limited extent 46%, considerably 38%).

² QA11: Do you think that the European set of values has influenced your own culture? (Choose one answer.)

Respondents were asked to what extent they agree or disagree with three different statements related to the importance of role of culture/cultural exchange: On the place of these in the EU, on their role in developing understanding and tolerance globally and on Europe’s ability to contribute to this. The exact statements are as follows³:

- ‘Culture and cultural exchanges should have a very important place in the EU so that citizens from different Member states can learn more from each other and feel more European’
- ‘Culture and cultural exchanges can play an important role in developing greater understanding and tolerance in the world, even when there are conflicts or tensions’
- ‘Europe, with its long-standing culture and values is particularly well placed to contribute to greater tolerance in the world’

- Cultural exchange seen as fostering greater tolerance, learning and understanding, both in Europe and the world -

2.3 Actions to further cross-cultural understanding

Throughout the survey, the place of increase exchange programs for students and teachers, such as Erasmus or Leonardo in cross-cultural understanding seem to have a crucial role when we examine results to a question where respondents were asked in which ways Turkish population and Europeans could be helped to know each other better.⁴

As showed below, the most frequently given answer is to increase exchange programs for students and teachers, such as Erasmus or Leonardo with this mentioned by over half (59%) of all asked the desire for cultural exchange is also an important aspect to develop the teaching of foreign languages at school. 56% would like to improve another language at least in part to be able to better understand people from other cultures.

Education, is seen as the key to furthering understanding across borders as in addition to the teaching of languages at school, the second most popular answer.

³ QA15: To what an extend do you agree with the following statements?

⁴ QA:16 - What would best help Europeans and neighbouring countries get to know each other better?

- Education seen as the best way to improve cross-cultural understanding within Europe -

At the same level, the implementation of programs allowing infrequent travellers to meet each other was chosen by 54% and supporting town twinning schemes is favoured by 46% respectively.

The arts are seen as playing a slightly less important role, for example supporting the touring of exhibitions and live performances beyond their national borders (34%) and 14% saying that supporting the production of TV documentaries and about other EU member states would increase understanding.

2.4 Sense of belonging

To ascertain the cultural horizons of individuals in Turkey, respondents were asked to what extent they describe their cultural identity and their cultural belonging at five geographical levels⁵:

- The respondent's own city/town/village
- The respondent's own region
- The respondent's own country
- Europe
- The world

- National belonging is the strongest feeling of Turkish population -

⁵ Q14: Please tell how attached you feel to: (Circle one answer in each line)

In a world of globalisation, instant communication pervious borders, how respondents claim identity in a competing tug-and-pull of global cultural homogenisation or fragmentation?

Firstly, **the majority of respondents say that they are feeling very attached to their country**, over three quarters (77%). Their cultural belonging is more concentrated at the national level, cultural attachment to their city is favoured by 'very attached' (40%) and attachment to their region is favoured by 'very attached' (31%).

The Turkish Republic was founded with the modernist idea of a nation-state therefore based on a common culture which is called Turkishness. The above-mentioned results reflect Turkish patriotism and the attachment to the Turkishness as national cultural identity.

Secondly, it is particularly interesting to note the high proportion of respondents answered to be less attached to Europe, said 'Not at all' (45%), 'Not very' (26%) and Don't' (17%). Despite the westernisation of Turkish socio-political system with the reform of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk and the European influence on Turkish *modus vivendi* the sense of belonging or not belonging to Europe is considered as a paradox to the Turkish identity. Those elements of Turkish identity that contrasted most with Europe, namely, religion and traditional culture seem to be determinant reasons to this result.

Finally, it can be seen that a high proportion of respondents are less interested and attached to the universalism/ the world 'not very' (25%), 'not at all' (19%) and 'don't' (22%). The cultural attachment to their own country is expressed by 92% of respondents, 12% for Europe (a gap of - 80 percentage points difference) and 34% for the World (-58 points percentage points difference). The cultural attachment to their country emphasises that the preservation of their traditional cultures and values are carefully secured from the tangle of globalisation.

2.5 Perception of European values

In the previous section, we can observe the clear evidence of the importance accorded to cultural exchange, both in fostering a feeling of cultural understanding and tolerance in general and more specifically in helping Turkish and EU citizens to learn from each other.

In this chapter, we turn to the issue of values. This is a major issue in the ongoing debate about the future of the EU, particularly in relation to the matter of Europe's perimeters. Arguments both for and against the potential membership of countries such as Turkey often revolve around ideas of the existence or not of common European values (i.e. values that are shared more by Europeans than by other peoples of the world).

Turkey's adhesion to the EU raises the question of the EU identity and value system. The EU's indecisiveness regarding this accession has underlined its continued uncertainty regarding which axiological path it will take.

According to the Treaty on European Union- any country wishing to join the EU must satisfy two conditions:⁶

- Be a state within geographical Europe; and
- Respect and commit to the values set out in Article 2 TEU, which call for respect for: human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality and the rule of law; human rights, including the rights

⁶ European Commission (2016), 'European Neighbourhood Policy And Enlargement Negotiations'. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/policy/glossary/terms/accession-eu_en

of persons belonging to minorities; and a pluralistic society and for non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men (Article 2 of TEU).

Therefore, firstly, we will study the question of which fundamental values of Europe is perceived as European and should be reinforced in society. Taking these respondent-identified core values, we will then examine whether these are seen as being European values or more universal human rights principles.

The idea of a 'European culture' is a complicated one, on which it is possible to take a number of standpoints. The European Union's fundamental values are respect for human dignity and human rights, freedom, democracy, equality and the rule of law. These values unite all the member states – no country that does not recognise these values can belong to the Union⁷.

- Rule of Law and Democracy are especially seen as being particularly European -

Respondents were presented with a list of 7 values and asked whether they thought the value in question is best represented by Europe⁸. Results to this subsequent exercise are therefore extremely useful in ascertaining what values are seen as being particularly European.

The most designated EU's fundamental value is 'rule of law', favoured by 42% of respondents. Slightly lower in the second position 'democracy' expressed by 41%, just under these two values, 'none of them' was chosen by 35% of those polled. The political stability of EU is perceived as the weak point of EU fundamental value mentioned by only 12% of respondents. The Human rights which is considered as the most important core value of EU according to the Copenhagen criteria⁹, was chosen only by 33% of respondents. In order to study the Human rights issue more in-depth, respondents were asked if the EU contribute to the protection of Human Rights worldwide¹⁰.

⁷ Mosaiikki ry (2014), 'Values'. Available at: <http://europarlamenti.info/en/values-and-objectives/values/>

⁸ QA9: What are some of the values that you associate with the EU? (Choose as many as you like)

⁹ Eur-Lex, 'Accession criteria (Copenhagen criteria)'. Available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/summary/glossary/accession_criteria_copenhagen.html

¹⁰ QA:12 Do you think that the EU contributes to the protection of human rights worldwide? (Choose one answer)

We can observe the perception differ between gender. The double-standards, discrimination and non-representation of Human Rights principles in the EU is more highlighted by men (78% vs. 22% of women 56 percentage points of differences). To a lesser extent, women have a better perception than men of EU as the protector Human Rights (58% vs. 42% of men; 16 percentage points of differences). As can be observed in the table below, the **EU advocates and applies human rights in a selective manner and has double-standards, was chosen by a high proportion (39%) of respondents.**

	Male	Female	Difference (female/male)
<i>Yes, the EU itself is based on the ideals of human rights</i>	42%	58%	-16
<i>Yes, the EU advocates human rights but the EU applies them in a selective manner and has double-standards</i>	56%	44%	-12
<i>No, the EU is shifting to nationalism and xenophobia</i>	70%	30%	-40
<i>No, the key issue in the EU actions is self-interest and it is that, not human rights, that motivates the EU</i>	78%	22%	-56

Note: Figures shown = % of males/females mentioning value

Respondents were asked what values they associate with the EU.¹¹ The results about societal value associated with Europe show a high prioritisation of injustice/double standards, which was largely chosen by 30% of respondents.

According to many respondents, a possible reason for this result seems to be the non-accession of Turkey to EU despite 54 years of waiting which is perceived by Turkish population as a double standards/ injustice while economically and politically less stable neighbourhood countries of Turkey are EU member countries. The EU is much more associated with socio-economical values such as wealth is mentioned by high proportions of respondents (29%) and growth (23%).

Indifference ranks in joint third position with growth is especially valued as 23%. The high proportion level of indifference as EU value is mostly related to the latest refugee crisis especially Syrian refugee crisis which was expressed by some respondents.

¹¹ QA10: What are some of the values that you associate with the EU? (Choose as many as you like)

War/interventionism was chosen by 19%, while peace was chosen only by 14% of respondents. The respondents expressed that the EU political intervention in EU candidate countries, military intervention in international conflicts outside of Europe is related to war/interventionism.

Values related to the education such as learning was favoured by 16% and creativity by 19%. On the opposite side, ignorance was chosen by only 5% of respondents. The positive connotation values such as responsibility (6%), wisdom (1%), optimism (0%), compassion (0%) are of a low magnitude, considered even as non-existent.

Thus in the public mind, it is very much the case that there is a core set of values (positive or negative) that define European society in a distinct manner, which is sometimes contradictorily shaped by history, medias and social interaction.

Societal values such as wealth and growth are seen as European values to preserve. Injustice/ double standard and indifference are especially seen as key societal the value to reinforce.

Perception of European Societal Values

3. Science Diplomacy

Science is an inherently borderless activity and international cooperation between scientists has existed for a long time. One of the international actors investing heavily into the development of a science diplomacy is the European Union.

The EU strategy for international scientific cooperation focuses on two dimensions. First, the research programs carried out by the EU are open to participation by research institutions and researchers worldwide. Second, the EU is developing targeted strategies – multiannual roadmaps – with selected countries in order to achieve specific objectives¹².

The scientific cooperation between EU and Turkey is conducted by the Scientific and Technological Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK) which has been assigned officially by the Turkish government as the contact organisation for the EU Framework Programmes at the beginning of 2003. The implementation of the national coordination role concerning the EU Framework Programmes is achieved by TÜBİTAK EU Framework Programmes National Coordination Office (NCO).

In this chapter, we will study the perception of European scientific cooperation initiatives and EU science diplomacy in Turkey. More precisely, the degree to which Turkish population notice European science cooperation and the perception women in science.

3.1 Perception of EU Science Diplomacy

Scientific cooperation with neighbourhood countries aims to strengthen the European Union's attractiveness and competitiveness, tackle global societal challenges and support EU external policies. Science diplomacy is also an increasingly important tool to ease cooperation with neighbourhood countries.

In order to figure out the perception and the knowledge of Turkish population about EU's scientific effort in Turkey, a series of similar questions were asked. We have – where relevant – cross-analysed the answers.

¹² European Parliamentary Research Service (2015), 'EU Scientific Cooperation with Third Countries', *EPRS Briefing*. Available at: https://era.gv.at/object/document/1957/attach/EPRS_BRI_July2015_564393_EN_pd.pdf

Respondent were asked 'How is the EU involved in shaping scientific efforts in your country?'¹³.

Men (%70) are more likely than women (30%) to cite that 'the EU is not involved at all' in shaping scientific efforts in Turkey. On the other hand, Women (76%) are more enthusiastic than men (26%) to say that 'the EU is closely involved'. The result shows that Turkish women recognise positively the EU's influence on scientific efforts in Turkey comparing to the men.

	Male	Female	Difference (female/male)
<i>It is not involved at all</i>	70%	30%	-40
<i>It is somewhat involved</i>	63%	37%	-26
<i>It is closely involved</i>	26%	74%	-48
<i>I don't know</i>	1%	0%	-1

Note: Figures shown = % of males/females mentioning value

Following this result, in the perspective to have in-depth insight about the perception of Turkish population on the EU scientific cooperation efforts in Turkey, respondents were asked to express their opinion on science cooperation between the EU and Turkey.¹⁴

As can be seen from the chart above, **a slight majority 38% say that 'The EU is not an important partner for my country'**. This figure is 10% higher than opposite view that says that 'the EU is the most important partner for my country' (28%), slightly below the 26% who expressed that 'the EU is the second or third most important partner of my country', while 8% of all respondents has no idea about the issue.

Scientific cooperation is mostly considered as politically neutral and universal. Therefore, since recent years science diplomacy is currently on the rise, both in the government policy and academic domains. Scientific cooperation with third countries aims to strengthen the European Union's attractiveness and competitiveness, tackle global societal challenges and support EU external policies¹⁵.

¹³ QA1: How is the EU involved in shaping scientific efforts in your country?

¹⁴ QA3: Which statement about the science cooperation between your country and the EU do you agree with? (Choose one answer)

¹⁵ European Parliament Think Tank (2015), 'EU scientific cooperation with third countries'. Available at: [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.html?reference=EPRS_BRI\(2015\)564393](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document.html?reference=EPRS_BRI(2015)564393)

The evaluation of the EU's scientific actions in Turkey¹⁶ is viewed by **over half of the vast majority of respondents (58%) as an interference to Turkish internal affairs**, 33% of respondents expressed that 'The level of the EU's intervention is acceptable, but I have some reservations about the implementations', 7% say that 'The EU's actions are appropriate and good', and 2% don't know. The results mentioned in the chart below emphasise that scientific actions are not perceived as politically neutral and create confusion in the public opinion.

In order to figure out the reasons of this confusion and to determine the knowledge of respondents about the EU's scientific actions in Turkey, respondents were asked in which ways the EU partners cooperate with their country in the field of science¹⁷.

We can observe in the chart below that the most frequently given answer by 33% of respondents is 'none of them' which can be interpreted that they were not satisfied with the proposed categories, slightly below 27% express that 'scientific priorities of my country are influenced by preferences of the EU', 21% of respondents say that 'scientists from my country receive funds from the EU to perform their research', 15% express that 'scientists from my country and those from the EU cooperate on common projects' and finally 5% 'don't know'.

¹⁶ Q5: Judging from the scientific cooperation between your country and the EU only, how do you evaluate the EU's actions? (Choose one answer)

¹⁷ Q2: What are the ways in which the EU partners cooperate with your country in the field of science? (Choose at least one answer)

3.2 Benefits of Science Cooperation

So as to ascertain views on the advantages of scientific cooperation, respondents were asked to define the benefits of scientific cooperation with the EU for their country.¹⁸

The high proportion of respondents (45%) indicate that the benefit of scientific cooperation with EU is 'improved knowledge'. 27% say they 'don't know', slightly below 'there are no benefit' was chosen by 17% and 'development of global science' by 12%. It is interesting to note that scientific cooperation is seen neither as mean for cultural understanding (0%) nor as an economic benefit or access to funds (0%). **The result highlight that scientific cooperation is perceived as an exchange/ synergy for the improvement of the knowledge.** Nevertheless, the high rate of 'don't know' show that scientific actions and cooperation are not clear in the public mind due to a lack of communication/information.

Finally, to obtain a clearer view of how the surveyed perceive the reasons behind the EU scientific cooperation with neighbourhood countries, respondents were asked to what extent their own views correspond to a series of statements relating to the reasons for the EU's effort in international scientific cooperation.¹⁹

Interestingly, the high proportion of respondents (42%) indicate that **'The EU is seeking cooperation with international partners to convince others of the EU political or economic agenda. The EU wants to appear stronger than others'**. 18% say that 'The EU is seeking cooperation to create a platform for scientific cooperation', placing this category in joint second rank 18% 'don't know', the option 'others' was favoured by 12%, slightly below 11% say that 'The EU is cooperating in science because the US, China, Australia and other actors'.

¹⁸ QA4: What are the benefits of scientific cooperation with the EU for your country? (Choose as many as you like)

¹⁹ QA6: What do you think are the reasons for the EU's effort in international scientific cooperation? (Choose one answer)

In this section, we tried to figure out the perception and the knowledge of Turkish population about EU's scientific effort in Turkey. We can say that Turkish population has some reluctances about the EU scientific cooperation with Turkey. The results show that the lack of communication/ information seems to be the main source of this misunderstanding and lack of confidence to the EU seems to be another obstacle to be solved.

3.3 Gender Issue

The European Commission has actively fostered gender equality and the integration of a gender dimension in research funding since 1999. The first European Commission Communication on 'Women and Science' was primarily aimed at assisting women to better fit the requirements of academic professions. While support measures to individual scientists are still beneficial for advancing individual careers, gender equality policy has turned its aim towards more sustainable, institutional change in research-performing and research-funding organisations through the European Research Area, and with funding through the 7th framework programme and Horizon2020²⁰.

Gender equality in science is also an important issue for EU scientific cooperation with third countries. In this perspective, we tried to study how gender equality is perceived and the impact of science cooperation on women status²¹.

The above results emphasise the importance of scientific cooperation on women status. **More than half of all respondents (57%) say that 'scientific cooperation encourages women to make better use of their potential and advance their traditional role.** In the second rank, only 15% of respondents say that scientific activities are not compatible with women traditional position, ranks in joint second with those who answered 'women's engagement in scientific activities does not impact their status' (15%).

The oldest age group is more sceptical on the impact of scientific cooperation on women status (56% amongst those aged 40-59; 11% amongst those aged 18-24; 45 points difference). The youngest age group which are more involvement in EU scientific projects are more enthusiastic about its impact.

²⁰ European Commission (2013), 'Gender Equality Policies in Public Research'. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/pdf/199627_2014%202971_rtd_report.pdf

²¹ QA7: Does scientific cooperation affect the status of women? (Choose one answer)

We can conclude that **the involvement of Turkish women in science is perceived as a way for improving its traditional roles.**

Women empowerment in science remain as a major challenge for the EU. In Turkey, gender equality is still a major source of concern and women empowerment in science is seen as a crucial step for overcoming the gender gap. Respondents were asked to compare the situation of women scientists in their country and in the EU.²²

Women scientists in Europe are perceived as more empowered than in Turkey expressed by 49% of respondents. 19% of respondents think that the position of women scientists in Turkey is about the same with EU, slightly below 18% say they 'don't know' and only 15% say that women scientists are more empowered in Turkey. However, men (76%) are more likely than women (24%) to cite that 'Women scientists are more empowered in my country' (52 points difference). While women are directly concerned by this question and see weaknesses in women empowerment in Turkey comparing to Europe, men surprisingly have better perception about the issue.

²² QA 8: How do you compare the position of women scientists in the EU and in your country? (Choose one answer)

4. Empirical Results from the qualitative Interviews

Interviews have been conducted in Turkey with people (15) engaged in European programmes, people having benefited from those programmes, or people well aware of the existence of them.

The interviews provided us with a breadth of insights about the impact of scientific cooperation between the EU and Turkey. The answers of participants allowed us to draw a rather detailed picture of how they perceive the EU and how they have experienced and see the influence of EU science cooperation.

The following sections present the results of the interviews in a systematic manner. We have grouped the answers into overarching themes that inform us about:

- Perception and involvement in EU projects
- The influence of the EU projects
- Obstacles and problems that participants experienced in EU projects

4.1 Perception and involvement in EU projects

Most of the interviewees see the relevance of the EU projects and science cooperation in terms of scientific development of their country and they emphasise that this cooperation is beneficial for the knowledge transfer and as well for the cultural exchange. However, they were more sceptical about the social and economic relevance of the projects. They expressed that despite years of science cooperation and cultural exchange EU consider Turkish partners as 'third-world country' partners and the prejudgment is the main source of cultural misunderstanding.

The relevance of the EU projects for the scientific community specifically seems to be appreciated more by the participants. They referred to results such as creating scientific synergy with EU partners, increased scientific capacity, access to EU data, opening of new perspectives for their professional and individual development. The critics is mostly based on lack of information about the new EU projects and the complicated procedure.

According to the respondents interviewed, collaboration with EU projects improved the reputation and visibility of their institutes. A positive evaluation by EU partners gave them a competitive advantage. One participant mentioned that people who participate in European projects can more easily find employment in other sectors due to his knowledge about EU procedures.

4.2 The influence of the EU projects

In terms of impact on society, economy and cultural exchanges the views are quite divided. Half of the interviewees thought the projects they worked on were relevant to social development as well cultural exchanges and half thought that they were relevant to the development of key sectors of the economy. This seems to reflect that different projects can both set and achieve different goals.

All of our respondents agreed that participation in the EU programs translated into a wider change in understanding of European values in Turkey. Traditional values were considered the most important unifying factor for the Turkish society. Thanks to EU projects some also saw a positive change in the attitudes and understanding of EU values within the Turkish society and decision makers.

The majority of interviewees emphasised that Turkey belongs to the European culture and that European values are not foreign to Turkish society. Nevertheless, the EU cultural prejudice and non-adhesion of Turkey to the EU create a feeling of hostility towards the EU and a rejection of EU values.

It is difficult to assess the influence of EU projects on social developments and cultural understanding on the basis of our interviews. However, it is clear that the interviewees appreciate the EU for giving them the opportunity to work on the collaborative projects, but it is not clear to what extent these projects were able to make known the EU values.

A couple of respondents noted that there is a limited change in attitudes and understanding of the EU among policy makers, who have slowly started to adapt their standpoint on EU value. One respondent emphasised the change within the public institutions, where the institutes that collaborate with the EU have become more accessible, transparent and progressive.

The influence of EU's fundamental values such as rule of law, democracy and gender equality has highlighted by the majority of interviewees to be the most important values which have a real impact on the Turkish society thanks to EU membership process and EU projects. One interviewee expressed that the EU projects can contribute to spreading democratic values further as common values.

The interviewees which were involved in EU projects such as Erasmus, Horizon 2020, twinning city projects said that these projects have a real impact on cultural exchange and cultural understanding.

Education is seen as the most important tool for the rapprochement of Turkish and EU citizens, for the socio-economic development of the society and the emancipation women.

4.3 Obstacles and problems that participants experienced in EU projects

The interviewees identified many obstacles and problems regarding participation in the collaborative projects as follows:

- The lack of communication/information about the announcement of the new EU projects
- The complicated procedure of application to the EU projects.
- The absence of support for application to the EU projects from the Turkish authorities and universities.
- Insufficient methodological and analytical skills of Turkish population were also cited as a barrier to participation in EU projects.
- Structural obstacles to participation in the programmes for academic mobility and scientific cooperation with the EU such as visa problem.
- The lack of resources also affects the situation of the researchers.
- The interviewees also cited the problem lack of experience and support for writing high quality research proposals in order to be competitive.
- The strict bureaucratisation of EU funding constitutes a real barrier.

5. Conclusion

The results of this survey show important insights into the relationship Turkish citizens have with culture, both in terms of their behaviour and their opinions.

Firstly, we have seen how Turkish population conceive of the very idea of culture itself. Here the most common concept is one that particularly Traditions/languages/customs and values and beliefs ((including philosophy and religion).

Whatever associations respondents may have with culture, it is clear that most see it as playing an important role for the society. Over three-quarters (77%) expressed that they are feeling very attached to their country /national culture 'Turkishness'. It is particularly interesting to note the high proportion of respondents saying that to be less attached to Europe in total 88% of respondents. We can say that despite the westernisation of Turkish political system and the European influence on Turkish modus vivendi the sense of belonging or not belonging to Europe is considered as a paradox to the Turkish identity.

We also see that the bulk of Turkish citizens are convinced in the value of culture and cultural exchange: 71% say that 'cultural exchange seen as fostering greater tolerance, learning and understanding, both in Europe and the world'. In principle, this forms a resounding confirmation of the recent European Commission Communication, which calls for greater intercultural dialogue and development of cultural diplomacy.

The majority of respondents (surveyed and interviewed) see an important role for education. Education is seen as the key to furthering understanding across borders as in addition to the teaching of languages at school. Exchange programmes for students and teachers, such as Erasmus or Leonardo mentioned by over half (59%) of all asked the desire for cultural exchange. At the same level the implementation of programmes allowing infrequent travellers to meet each other is favoured by 54% and supporting town twinning schemes is favoured by 46% respectively.

The perception of EU key fundamental and societal values is important to comprehend the image of Europe in the Turkey. The most designated EU's fundamental value is 'rule of law, favoured by 42% of respondents, slightly lower in the second position 41% cited 'democracy. Nevertheless, concerning the issue of Human rights, the majority of respondents expressed that EU advocates and applies human rights in a selective manner and has double-standards.

Thus in the public mind it is very much the case that there is set of societal values (positive or negative) that define European society in a distinct manner which is sometimes contradictory shaped by history, perception medias and social interaction. According to Turkish perception, wealth and growth most all socio-economical values are seen as determinant of European values to preserve. Injustice/ double standard and indifference are especially seen as key societal the value to reinforce.

Overall, the picture that emerges from the survey and the interviews, the scientific cooperation between the EU and Turkey in a very positive light, with many stimulating developments spurred on by participation in joint projects.

The benefits, as perceived by Turkish citizen conform with prior expectations – participation in networks, advancement in research methodology, opportunities for the mobility of researchers, some transfer of technologies and know-how. However, the EU and its member states are considered to be not an important partner for Turkey highlighted by 38% of surveyed.

Scientific cooperation is mostly considered as politically neutral and universal. Therefore, since recent years, science diplomacy is currently on the rise, both in the government policy and academic domains. Over half of the respondents (58%) sees scientific cooperation with EU as an interference to Turkish internal affairs. The results underline that EU scientific actions are not perceived as politically neutral and create some confusion in the public opinion. The results show that Turkish population has some reluctances about the EU scientific cooperation with Turkey. It is interesting to note that scientific cooperation is seen neither as mean for cultural understanding (0%) nor as an economic benefit or access to funds (0%). The high proportion of respondents (42%) indicate that 'The EU is seeking cooperation with international partners to convince others of the EU political or economic agenda. The EU wants to appear stronger than others'.

The most positive influence and benefits cited by the majority of respondents is the influence of science cooperation on women status. The involvement of Turkish women in science is perceived as a way for improving its traditional roles.

Scientific cooperation works as an instrument of diplomacy and socialisation beyond the borders of scientific communities. More importantly, as noted by almost all interview respondents, scientific cooperation in EU-funded projects helped them and their organisations for the knowledge transfer, improve their professional situation and establish long lasting scientific networks.

Finally, the EU perception on cultural and science diplomacy has positive image in the mind of Turkish people who involved directly in EU project but for the majority of the population who are not involved in EU projects this perception is negative. This population is more influenced by political rhetoric and they have some reluctances about cultural and science cooperation with Europe which they consider as a hidden agenda and as interference to their internal affairs. We can conclude that the lack of communication/ information around EU and Turkey cultural and science cooperation seems to be the main source of this misunderstanding and should be resolved for improving the diplomatic, cultural and scientific relations.

About the author

Associate Professor N. Selin Senocak is Political Scientist, Chair Holder of the UNESCO Chair on Cultural Diplomacy, Governance and Education, Director at the Diplomatic and Strategic Studies Centre Turkey and Researcher for the European Leadership in Cultural, Science and Innovation Diplomacy (EL-CSID) project. She served as Deputy Dean at the École Polytechnique de Lausanne – EPFL (Swiss Federal Institute of Technology). She was the Founding Director of Occidental Studies Applied Research Centre at Istanbul Aydin University (IAU).

The EL-CSID project
is coordinated
by the
Institute for European Studies (IES)
www.el-csid.eu

Institute for European Studies
Pleinlaan 5
B-1050 Brussels
T: +32 2 614 80 01
E: info@ies.be
www.ies.be

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 693799.